

INFLUENCE OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF WOVEN HEMP/EPOXY COMPOSITE

D. de Vasconcellos^{1*}, F. Sarasini², M. Pucci¹, F. Touchard¹, L. Chocinski-Arnault¹, C. Santulli², J. Tirillo²

¹ Département de Physique et Mécanique des Matériaux, Institut Pprime CNRS ISAE-ENSMA, Poitiers, France, ² Department of Chemical Engineering Materials and Environment, Sapienza Università di Roma, Rome, Italy

* Corresponding author (davi.vasconcellos@ensma.fr)

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1 General introduction

During recent years, as a result of environmental and economical concerns, there is a growing interest in the use of natural fiber reinforced composites. Plant fibers are good ecological candidates for substitution of synthetic ones such as glass and Kevlar in terms of specific mechanical properties in composite materials [1][2]. But knowledge of their resistance to impact, though important for semi-structural applications, is still scarce [3].

The purpose of this work is to study the resistance to low velocity impact of woven hemp/epoxy matrix composites and the influence of impact damage on their residual quasi-static tensile and cyclic fatigue strength. Drop weight impact tests were performed on woven hemp/epoxy composite specimens and analysis of impact behavior and the characterization of damage modes were carried out. Then, impacted specimens were tested in quasi-static and cyclic fatigue tensile loadings.

This study comes from collaboration between the Department of Chemical Engineering Materials and Environment at Sapienza University, in Rome, Italy, and the Département de Physique et Mécanique des Matériaux of Pprime Institute at ISAE-ENSMA, in Poitiers, France.

2 Materials and testing methods

2.1 Material

The studied composite material is a lay-up of 7 plies of a plain woven hemp fabric impregnated with epoxy resin. The hemp fabric is non-treated, has a weight of 267 ± 1 g/m², has three hemp yarns in each

warp and weft thread and has a thread count of 60x40 (warp per weft per inch). The hemp yarns have apparent diameter of 300 ± 60 μm, linear density of 83 tex and are composed of hemp fibers with diameter of 13 ± 5 μm and twist level of 324 tpm. The epoxy resin is an EPOLAM 2020 from Axson Technologies with density of 1.10 g/cm³ (according to the manufacturer data-sheet).

The composite plates were manufactured at the company Valagro, France, by vacuum infusion technique, where the resin is infused under vacuum of 30 mbar. The hemp fabric is pre-dried at 40°C for 24h. The plates were cured at ambient temperature for 24h and then by the following post-curing cycle: 3h at 40°C, 2h at 60 °C, 2h at 80°C and 4h at 100°C, which resulted in composite plates with density of around 1.2 ± 0.1 g/cm³, thickness of 4.8 ± 0.1 mm, fiber content of $30 \pm 5\%$ by volume and maximum void content of around 9%.

2.2 Testing methods

2.2.1 Impact tests

Impact tests were performed by using a falling dart impact testing machine, model Fractovis Plus from CEAST (Pianezza - TO, Italy). The specimens were tested at three impact energy levels (2.5, 5 and 10 J) by keeping constant the indenter mass (6.929 kg) with an hemispherical impact head (diameter equal to 12.7 mm). The impact testing was performed on 6 specimens of 50 mm x 50 mm and other 6 rectangular specimens of 50 mm x 150 mm. Four specimens were tested for each energy level, for impact test characterizations and static tensile tests of post-impacted specimens. Then 9 specimens were impacted at 5J to perform post-impact fatigue tests.

2.2.2 Tensile tests

Samples of 30 mm x 150 mm were cut from impacted specimens at each energy level and submitted to tensile loading at constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The specimens impacted at 5J were tested in tension-tension fatigue with stress ratio (R) of 0.01, frequency of 1Hz and at three levels of maximum stress (σ_{max}): 80%, 60% and 40% of the ultimate tensile stress (UTS) of the 5J impacted specimen (σ_{5J}).

2.2.3 Damage characterization

Internal damage of impacted specimens was studied by optical microscopy. The two optical digital microscope systems used are a Leica Microsystems device, which allows up to six times magnification and a Reichert-Jung system, which enables up to 1000 times magnification.

Damage development during fatigue tests was monitored by acoustic emission (AE), using an AMSY-5 AE system by Vallen Systeme GmbH (Icking, Germany). To allow linear localization of signals, two broad-band (100-1500 kHz, Fujicera 1045S, diameter = 20 mm) PZT AE sensors were placed at both ends of specimens using silicon grease for coupling, at a distance of 50 mm.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Impact tests

3.1.1 Impact tests parameters

Fig. 1 presents the impact contact force-deflection curve of a specimen impacted at 5J. In this curve, contact force is the impact load undergone by the specimen; and deflection is the indentation of the falling dart into specimen surface. This plot shows a closed loop, which is peculiar to specimens having rebound. The area under the curve is the deformation energy that is initially transferred from the dart to the specimen and then given back from the specimen to rebounding dart (recovered energy). From this curve, also other parameters were obtained, like peak load. These parameters, among others, are used to characterize the resistance to impact and enable comparison between different materials.

The peak load parameter indicates the maximum load that material can tolerate before undergoing major damage at a level of impact energy [9] and some data are available in literature. Fig. 2 presents a comparison of the peak load value for the tested hemp/epoxy composite and other fabric reinforced composites such as glass/epoxy [4], Kevlar/epoxy [5] and a similar hemp/epoxy [6]. Even though these data depend on the amount of fiber in the composite and also on the thickness of the samples, it shows that hemp fibers are comparable to synthetic fibers in terms of impact resistance of reinforced composites.

In the graph of Fig. 3, the ratio between recovered and absorbed energy is plotted for different impact energy levels and data from a similar hemp/epoxy composite [6] is added (dashed line). These results show that the energy absorbed by the specimen becomes higher than the restituted one, which represents growing impact damage for growing impact energy.

Fig. 1. Impact load-displacement curve of a composite hemp/epoxy specimen impacted at 5J.

Fig. 2. Comparison of our results for the impact peak load with other types of composites.

Fig. 3. Ratio between recovered and absorbed energy as a function of impact energy.

3.1.2 Impact damage characterization

Firstly, surface impact damage modes were analyzed and are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 for a specimen impacted at 5J. The picture in Fig. 4 shows the impacted surface (front face), where the damage is characterized by a circular indentation caused by the falling dart hemispherical head. The depth of this indentation increased with increasing impact energy and there were no visible cracks on the front face for the applied impact energy levels. The damage in the opposite surface (back face) is characterized by radial matrix cracks which tend to form a cross, which is likely to be due to the use of plain weave in the composite (Fig. 5). There was no perforation for the applied impact energies.

Moreover, impacted specimens were cut at the damaged zone through specimen thickness, with a diamond wire cutting process, and polished. Microscopic observation of the cross section revealed a conical shape of the internal damage, which grows from the front to the back surface (Fig. 6).

Fig. 4. Front face of impacted specimen at 5J.

Fig. 5. Back face of impacted specimen at 5J.

Fig. 6. Microscopic observation of the cross section of a 5J impacted specimen.

At higher magnification (Fig. 7) it was possible to distinguish two types of internal damage: matrix and interface cracks. No yarn or fiber breakage was found in any observed specimen, which may imply that the interface is not very strong.

Fig. 7. Internal damage of a 5J impacted specimen.

3.2 Static tensile tests

Impacted specimens at three impact energy levels (2.5, 5 and 10J) were tested in static tensile tests to analyze the influence of impact damage on the residual tensile strength and stiffness.

Fig. 8 presents the ultimate tensile stress (UTS) of as-manufactured and impacted specimens at the different energy levels. These tests indicated that tensile strength of the studied composite is reduced to about 85% after an impact of 2.5J, to 70% after an impact of 5J; and to about 60% after an impact of 10J.

One can also observe the increase of standard deviation in the UTS for impacted specimens compared to non-impacted ones (dashed lines). This

higher standard deviation is probably due a combination of the dispersion of the material tensile strength and the variation of impact resistance, which are due to natural dispersion of mechanical properties of plant fibers.

On the other hand, the stiffness of impacted specimens did not present significant change as it remains into the dispersion of non-impacted ones, which is represented by dashed lines in Fig. 9. This can be justified by the absence of reinforcement damage on impact tests at these energy levels, as showed by microscopic observations.

Fig. 8. Ultimate tensile stress of non-impacted and impacted specimens of woven hemp/epoxy composite.

Fig. 9. Young's modulus of non-impacted and impacted specimens of woven hemp/epoxy composite.

3.3 Fatigue tests

Based on results of impact tests and post-impact tensile tests, 5J impact energy level was selected for post-impact fatigue testing, since it produced significant but not close-to-failure damage, suggesting that after impact at 5J, the composite may still continue service.

The fatigue tests were performed on 9 impacted specimens for three fatigue stress levels (three specimens for each level), where the maximum fatigue stress (σ_{max}) represents 40%, 60% and 80% of the mean tensile strength of the 5J impacted specimens (σ_{5J}).

3.3.1 S-N curves

In Fig. 10, the number of cycles to failure for each tested specimen is plotted (circles) against the maximum fatigue stress normalized (σ_{max}) by the mean UTS of non-impacted specimens (σ_0). Also, results from previous fatigue tests [7] on non-impacted specimens of the same material is added (squares). For both impacted and non-impacted specimens results, the arrows represent specimens that did not fail after 10^6 fatigue cycles.

A power-law based model [8] was used to fit the experimental points (solid lines). And finally, the dashed lines represent the standard deviation for the power-law model, based on the standard deviation of the UTS of impacted and non-impacted specimens. These results show that fatigue strength decreases with the increase of fatigue stress levels for impacted and non-impacted composites, as expected. Also, for given fatigue stress level, the number of cycles to failure is reduced in impacted specimens compared to non-impacted ones.

Fig. 10. S-N fatigue curves for 5 J impacted and not impacted specimens of woven hemp/epoxy composite.

In Fig. 11, data from Fig. 10 are plotted again, but for the impacted specimens fatigue stress levels are represented in the secondary vertical axis, this time normalized by the mean UTS of impacted specimens (σ_{5J}). For non-impacted specimens, the stress levels are plotted in the primary Y axis, still normalized by the mean UTS of non-impacted specimens (σ_0).

This representation puts emphasis on the more significant dispersion of fatigue results for impacted specimens compared to non-impacted ones, as also found in tensile tests. Fig. 11 also shows that S-N curves of impacted and non-impacted specimens have similar shape when normalized by corresponding tensile strength. It means that, for the studied composite, the impact influence on fatigue behavior can be determined by the impact influence on its tensile strength, for low energy impact. This finding has been also observed by Yuanjian et al.[10] on glass fiber reinforced composites.

Fig. 11. S-N curves: normalized by the mean UTS of impacted specimens (σ_{5J}) for impacted specimens and by σ_0 for non-impacted specimens.

3.3.2 Acoustic Emission monitoring (AE)

AE events, which are related to formation of damage, were recorded during fatigue tests and are presented in Fig. 12, Fig. 13, Fig. 14 and Fig. 15. The vertical axis represents specimens gauge length between AE sensors and the horizontal axis represents the normalized fatigue cycles. Fig. 12, Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 represent impacted specimens tested in fatigue with stress levels of 40%, 60% and 80% relative to UTS of impacted specimens (σ_{5J}), respectively. Fig. 15 represents data from non-impacted specimen tested in fatigue with stress level of 80% of UTS of non-impacted specimens (σ_0)[7].

For impacted specimens and for all applied fatigue stress levels (Fig. 12, Fig. 13 and Fig. 14), the AE events are distributed all along fatigue lifetime, but they are concentrated in the impacted zone where also ultimate failure occurred, represented by a cross in the vertical axis. These three figures show also a growing amount of AE events for higher fatigue stress level.

For non-impacted specimens (Fig. 15), AE events are also distributed all along fatigue lifetime, however they are localized more uniformly throughout the specimen length.

Fig. 12. Spatial and time distribution of AE events recorded during fatigue test for impacted specimen subjected to $\sigma_{max} = 40\% \sigma_{5J}$.

Fig. 13. Spatial and time distribution of AE events recorded during fatigue test for impacted specimen subjected to $\sigma_{max} = 60\% \sigma_{5J}$.

Fig. 14. Spatial and time distribution of AE events recorded during fatigue test for impacted specimen subjected to $\sigma_{\max} = 80\% \sigma_{5J}$.

Fig. 15. Spatial and time distribution of AE events recorded during fatigue test for non-impacted specimen subjected to $\sigma_{\max} = 80\% \sigma_0$.

Another significant difference between AE events on impacted and non-impacted specimens during fatigue tests emerges in Fig. 16, where the normalized cumulative numbers of AE events for impacted and not impacted specimens are plotted against normalized fatigue cycles, for fatigue stress level of 80% of the respective UTS. In particular, the curve for the non-impacted specimens has a sudden and significant increase during initial cycles, then increases at a constant rate during most fatigue lifetime and quickly increases at final failure. On the other hand, the curve for the impacted specimens has

only a constant raise during most fatigue lifetime and a marked fast increase at final cycles.

Future work will be aimed at characterizing AE events to correlate them to different damage mechanisms and propose explanations for these observations.

Fig. 16. Normalized cumulative AE events number plotted against normalized fatigue cycles for impacted and non-impacted specimens.

4 Conclusions

Impact testing allowed characterizing different damage modes. Impact related parameters i.e., peak load, elastic energy, absorbed energy, were studied and compared to those found in the literature for other composites.

The influence of impact damage on the residual tensile strength and stiffness was also studied. Moreover, based on these results, 5J impact energy level was selected for post-impact fatigue testing.

At first, the fatigue behavior of non-impacted specimens was analyzed. Then, it has been compared with fatigue behavior of impacted specimens. Results show that, as expected, the fatigue life is reduced for impacted specimens. In these tests, fatigue damage located by acoustic emission was concentrated in the impacted zone, where also ultimate failure occurred

These results have enabled a better understanding of the influence of impact at energies not very close to penetration on the fatigue resistance of this woven hemp/epoxy composite.

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